

Arsenites

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On Christmas 1261 the Byzantine emperor Michael VIII Palaiologos had his eleven-year-old co-emperor John IV Laskaris blinded (thus losing the ability to claim the throne), exiled and imprisoned in Bithynia. This action led to Michael's excommunication by the patriarch Arsenios and, subsequently, to the Arsenite schism. Three years after his excommunication, the emperor deposed and exiled Arsenios, and in 1266 he enthroned Germanos III at the patriarchate. As a result, the former patriarch's supporters, the Arsenites, who considered his deposition uncanonical, refused to recognise any of the following patriarchs, considering their election invalid and illegal, and broke away from the church, remaining loyal to Arsenios and the Laskarids. This is why the movement was more influential in Asia Minor, while its social character should also be noted, as it mainly represented the lower social strata that had been favoured by Theodore II Laskaris, along with its political motives, since the Arsenites opposed Michael's usurpation of the throne, his indifference to the eastern provinces, and his ecclesiastical, economic and pro-aristocratic policy, alongside his role in the patriarch's enthronement and the extent to which an emperor could intervene in ecclesiastical affairs. Germanos soon resigned and was replaced by Joseph I who lifted Michael's excommunication, causing a conflict between his supporters, the Josephites, and the Arsenites. After Andronikos II, Michael's son, succeeded to the throne, he deposed the current unionist patriarch Bekkos and reinstated Joseph, thus giving control of the ecclesiastical affairs to the Josephites and at the same time embittering the Arsenites. Although they presented a greater threat though, Joseph had crowned Andronikos co-emperor, and therefore questioning the legality of his election would be impossible. After his death in 1283, Andronikos tried to compromise the two factions by choosing the scholar Gregory II of Cyprus for the patriarchate, thinking he would be accepted by both of them; both sides though opposed him, while the Arsenites were disappointed and felt deceived by the emperor. During Gregory's tenure, an effort was made to reconcile the two parties and bring the Arsenites, whose power had grown, back into the official church. In 1284 Andronikos convoked a church synod at Atramyttion, where it was eventually decided that it was up to God to judge which of them should rule the church by casting into a fire two volumes, each containing their opinions, and considering the one that would not be burnt the worthiest. As both were immediately burnt though, the two parties were temporarily appeased and agreed to accept Gregory. The following day though some of the most adamant Arsenites regretted this. As the members of the movement were divided into two groups, with the leading one emphasising its religious character and wishing to eventually gain positions in the church, and the majority of the members being interested in punishing those they considered to have sinned and prioritising a political opposition to the Palaiologoi, the emperor approached the former, and they agreed to accept the jurisdiction of the patriarchate of Constantinople on the condition that all the ordinations made by Bekkos would be annulled and those who had persecuted the Arsenites would be deposed. At the same time, the Arsenite movement had grown in Constantinople and its political nature was strengthened as it spread within the city, where anti-Latin and anti-Unionist sentiments prevailed and the people were also faced with heavy taxation and state arbitrariness, something that made their turn to the Arsenites, who were leading the social struggles of the time, easier. According to a letter to the emperor by the patriarch, they could freely gather in public places and propagate their ideas, convert new members even by force and defy the official church's rules. It seems that the party had gradually become one of simple opposition to the Palaiologoi and the official church, a religious, political and social movement that would often participate in riots and anti-government conspiracies. Andronikos however kept trying to reunite them, but they argued that they should take control of the church in order to cleanse it, as they had never been excommunicated, and that if their leader became patriarch, they would return to the official church. Subsequently, the emperor allowed

them to bring the body of Arsenios in Constantinople in order to rebury it with the honours appropriate for a patriarch, granted them the monastery of Mosele and later visited John Laskaris in Asia Minor and ameliorated his living conditions. The Arsenites though were still not satisfied, and in 1289 they contributed to Gregory's resignation, again hoping that one amongst them would be elected. Nevertheless, their demands, which included the election of a patriarch from their ranks, the removal of Joseph's name from the diptychs, the restoration of orthodoxy and the cancellation of previous excommunications, were so extreme that Andronikos could not accept them, and finally chose the monk Athanasios to be the next patriarch. The emperor was again under the impression that the latter would be accepted by both parties, but the Arsenites felt discontent, while Athanasios was also intransigent in dealing with them. He soon became very unpopular and abdicated in 1293. His successor was the more compromising monk John XII Kosmas, who, however, was also received with opposition, came into conflict with the emperor and eventually resigned in 1303. Andronikos negotiated with the Arsenites in order to appoint a patriarch they would approve, and they nominated an elderly bishop who had been ordained while Arsenios was patriarch and urged the emperor to overlook some of his irregularities since he had not taken part in any religious scandal. Although he initially agreed, he soon recalled Athanasios to the patriarchate because he was impressed by his prophetic abilities and because he wanted him to get an earlier implied anathema lifted, leaving the Arsenites feeling deceived once again. However, Athanasios' attitude towards the Arsenites had not changed, and therefore Andronikos' attempts to reunite them with the Byzantine church failed. In 1304 he called their leaders to a synod where he blamed them for dividing both the church and the society despite all his efforts and good will, and stated that since they did not question the doctrine, they had to obey the official hierarchy. Although some Arsenites claimed that they were only interested in the official church's purification and insisted that it was heretical because of its common liturgy with the Westerners, Andronikos asked them to return to the church and warned them that otherwise the responsibility for the schism would fall solely on them. However, they were not convinced and the council ended without an agreement. Eventually, the emperor decided that in order to end the controversy he had to replace Athanasios with a more compromising patriarch. In September 1309 the latter resigned, and in 1310, after lengthy negotiations with the Arsenites, he was replaced by Niphon. By that time the Arsenites had been weakened due to the loss of many territories, and therefore followers, in Asia Minor, and wished to return to the official church as they had realised that their opposition to it was leading nowhere. Since both Andronikos and Niphon also wanted to heal the schism, the Arsenites presented their terms which included repudiation of any other dogma, cancellation of earlier excommunications, removal of any members of the clergy that had practiced simony and of those that had been ordained by Bekkos, removal of Joseph's name from the diptychs, and guarantee that neither John XII nor Athanasios would be allowed to become patriarchs again. As they did not insist on their demand for the election of one of their number to the patriarchate, they indirectly recognised the legitimacy of the ecclesiastical hierarchy and the Palaiologan dynasty, a great relief for the emperor, who, until then, always had to take them into account whenever he made a political decision. The settlement took place in 1310 during a ceremony at Hagia Sophia, where Arsenios' corpse was brought and set up, dressed in patriarchal clothes and holding a document, according to which his excommunications were revoked, and the terms of their agreement, which Andronikos approved for the sake of ecclesiastical peace, were confirmed. The most intransigent among the Arsenites and the followers of the official church disagreed, while some of the former were again separated because they did not get the offices they wanted and which had been promised to them by Niphon; any reactions however were not taken into account. Thus, after forty-five years, the Arsenite schism that had divided both church and society and embodied religious, political and social phenomena, was resolved, and at the same time a danger to the church and the state was eliminated.

Date Range: 1265 CE - 1310 CE

Region: The Byzantine Empire

Region tags: Asia Minor, Eastern Mediterranean, Greece, Anatolia, Byzantium

The Byzantine Empire in the 13th century

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Goumaridis, P. Το Κίνημα Των Αρσενιατών (1261-1310). Ιδεολογικές Διαμάχες Την Εποχή Των Πρώτων Παλαιολόγων. Athens: Domos, 1999.
- Source 2: Kontogiannopoulou, A. “Το Σχίσμα Των Αρσενιατών (1265-1310). Συμβολή Στην Μελέτη Της Πορείας Και Της Φύσης Του Κινήματος.” Βυζαντικά 18 (1998): 177-235.
- Source 3: Sykoutris, I. “Περί Το Σχίσμα Των Αρσενιατών.” Ελληνικά 2 (1929): 267-332.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The same famine relief available to other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The same poverty relief available to other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The same care available to other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The same formal education available to other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The same public food storage provided for other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The same water management provided for other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The same transportation infrastructure provided for other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The same taxes levied on other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Interaction with the same institutionalized police force as other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Interaction with the same institutionalized judicial system as other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Arsenites were persecuted during Michael's reign.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Subjected to the same formal legal code as other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Participation in the same institutionalized military as other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Protected by or subject to the same institutionalized military as other Byzantines, e.g. not restricted to Arsenites' adherents.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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General References

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